

Weed flora in rice in Bhubaneswar (Orissa, India)

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Weeds seriously limit rice production at Bhubaneswar, Orissa. In 1985 wet season, we surveyed weeds in ricefields in uplands, medium lands, lowlands, and swampy and waterlogged fields, using random sampling of 10 farmers from each site type. From each field, we randomly selected five 1- × 1-m areas.

Only weeds common in all samples are reported here.

1. Uplands

Grasses: *Digitaria sanguinalis*, *Echinochloa colona*, *Eleusine indica*, *Eragrostis nutans*, *Panicum antidotale*, *Cynodon dactylon*.

Sedges: *Cyperus rotundus*, *C. iria*, *Eimbristylis dichotoma*.

Broadleaved weeds: *Senna obtusifolia*, *Crotalaria juncea*, *Celosia argentea*, *Sida rhombifolia*.

2. Medium lands

Grasses: *Echinochloa crus-galli*, *Eragrostis nutans*, *Paspalum conjugatum*.

Sedges: *Cyperus elatus*, *C. esculentus*, *C. brevifolius*.

Broadleaved weeds: *Murdannia nudiflora*, *Ludwigia perennis*, *Corchorus aestuans*, *Aeschynomene americana*, *A. aspera*.

The fern *Marsilea quadrifolia* was also found.

3. Lowlands

Eragrostis cilianensis, *Oryza* sp. (wild rice), *Cyperus exaltatus*, *Scirpus supinus*.

4. Swampy lands and waterlogged fields
Pistia stratiotes, *Glyceria* sp., *Glycine* sp., *Ulothrix* sp., *Spirogyra* sp., and *Chara* sp. □

Integrated weed and water management in transplanted rice

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We studied weed control and water use efficiency (WUE) with three irrigation

regimes and six weed control treatments (see table) in transplanted rice during 1985-86 dry (DS) and wet (WS) seasons. The treatments were in a split-plot design, replicated three times.

Weeds at the experimental site (sandy clay loam) were *Echinochloa colona*, *E. crus-galli*, *Cyperus rotundus*, *C. iria*, *C. difformis*, *Fimbristylis miliacea*, *Eclipta alba*, *Ammannia baccifera*, *Marsilea quadrifolia*, *Monochoria vaginalis*, and

Ludwigia paryzflora.

WUE was better with 5-cm continuous submergence than with irrigation with 5-cm water 1 d after water disappeared, saving 40% water in WS and 33% in DS. Grain yields were comparable.

Among weed control treatments, preemergence butachlor (1.25 kg ai/ ha) plus postemergence 2,4-D (sodium salt) (0.75 kg ai/ ha) effectively controlled

Effect of weed control treatments under different irrigation regimes on grain yield, weed dry matter, water use efficiency, and total water requirement of transplanted rice, Madurai, India, 1985-86.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)		Weed dry matter at harvest (g/m ²)		Water use efficiency (kg/ha per cm)		Total water requirement (cm)	
	WS IR50	DS IR20	WS IR50	DS IR20	WS IR50	DS IR20	WS IR50	DS IR20
<i>Irrigation regimes</i>								
5 cm continuous submergence	7.0	5.9	10	26	43	62	166	94
5 cm submergence 1 d after water disappeared	6.9	5.8	14	32	61	92	100	63
Maintenance of 5 cm submergence at reproductive stage and 5 cm submergence 1 d after disappearance at vegetative and ripening stages	6.6	5.4	15	33	50	65	131	83
LSD (0.05)	0.3	0.4	0.9	ns	—	—	1.4	1.2
<i>Weed control methods</i>								
Unweeded check	5.8	4.9	34	75	44	60	136	84
HW 15 and 30 DT	7.2	6.0	9	20	57	78	132	80
Butachlor 1.25 kg ai/ha + HW 30 DT	7.1	5.8	9	24	56	74	132	80
Thiobencarb 1.50 kg ai/ha + HW 30 DT	6.9	5.6	10	23	55	73	132	80
Butachlor 1.25 kg ai/ha + 2,4-D (sodium salt) 0.75 kg ai/ha 30 DT	7.5	6.2	8	18	60	81	131	79
Thiobencarb 1.50 kg ai/ha + 2,4-D (sodium salt) 0.75 kg ai/ha 30 DT	6.8	3.6	9	22	54	73	131	81
LSD (0.05)	0.8	0.4	1.7	1.5	—	—	0.6	2.0
Interaction (weed control × irrigation)								
LSD (0.05)	ns	ns	ns	ns	—	—	ns	ns